

EFFECTIVENESS OF ANTIHELMINTIC MEDICINES IN THE TREATMENT OF FASCIOLYSIS IN GOATS IN THE CONDITIONS OF SURKHANDARYO REGION

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Currently, in the fight against and prevention of fascioliasis in goats, it is necessary to pay attention to its regional epizootological characteristics, bioecology, and the intensity of invasion of pathogens. It is also advisable to improve the methods of prevention and treatment of the disease based on the mechanism of action of the tested drugs, their application processes, and cost.

The majority of livestock, especially goats, currently kept in the Republic of Uzbekistan is kept in the care of the population, therefore, all personal assistants, farmers and farms require timely, high-quality and planned implementation of treatment and preventive measures against helminthiasis and other dangerous parasitic diseases. Today, the territory of the Republic of Uzbekistan has created a large number of private veterinary pharmacies, and wide opportunities have been created for the import of many new anthelmintic and other medicinal products from abroad. Currently, these pharmacies have anthelmintic drugs of various forms and compositions used against helminthiasis, in particular, helminths of small horned animals. Among them, albendazole, which is inexpensive and its various pharmaceutical forms, is currently one of the most widely used medicinal anthelmintic agents in veterinary practice for the treatment of fascioliasis in goats. Also, in current production practice, veterinary specialists or animal owners are using these drugs unplanned, in excess of the norm, many times, and in some cases, the same anthelmintic is repeatedly used on animals every month. Such unplanned deworming activities cause a number of unpleasant situations, such as increased costs, poisoning of the animal body, as well as harm to the quality of products obtained from animals and their health due to their consumption by humans. When treating fascioliasis in goats, it is advisable, first of all, to take into account the season and type of trematode that causes it, the intensity of the invasion, and the course of the disease, based on the regional epizootological characteristics of this disease, and to select anthelmintic drugs and determine the duration of their use.

For many years, preparations such as carbon tetrachloride, hexachloroethane, hexachloroparaxylene, hexychol, bithionol, sulfen, diamphenetide, zani, fazinex, dovenix, rafoxanide, dertil have been used to treat fascioliasis in goats. However, in recent years, the influx of new medicinal substances from foreign countries has increased, and the improvement in the quality of private veterinary pharmacies has created the opportunity to recommend several types of drugs for a particular disease. As a result, the type of drugs used against fascioliasis has changed, and the old anthelmintics have been replaced by combined ones with new properties. Examples of such new chemical preparations include all

albendazole preparations (alben, albasafe, albendazole, albenol, helmintol, albazen, albendex, bendaz, etc.), rolenol, brontel-10, closan-50, closantel, faskotsid, helmicid, and many other chemical preparations.

Conclusions:

1. For many years, preparations such as carbon tetrachloride, hexachloroethane, hexachloroparaxylene, hexychol, bithionol, sulfen, diamphenetide, zanyl, fazinex, dovenix, rafoxanide, dertil have been used to treat fascioliasis in goats. However, in recent years, the influx of new medicinal substances from foreign countries has increased, and the quality of private veterinary pharmacies has improved, which has made it possible to recommend several types of drugs for a particular disease. As a result, the type of drugs used against fascioliasis has changed, and the old anthelmintics have been replaced by combined ones with new properties. Examples of such new chemical preparations include all albendazole preparations (alben, albasafe, albendazole, albenol, helmintol, albazen, albendex, bendaz, etc.), rolenol, brontel-10, closan-50, closantel, faskotsid, helmicid, and many other chemical preparations.

2. Taking into account the extensive and intensive effectiveness of all the used anthelmintic drugs against fascioliasis in goats, when conditionally evaluating their effectiveness, we note Rolenol injection solution in the first place, Albendazole 10% suspension in the second place, and Alben tablets in the third place. However, when analyzed in terms of economic cost and average cost, Metsalben suspension is a relatively cheap and convenient drug to use. Closantel-50 solution is also a relatively cheap and convenient anthelmintic.

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